

CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool. Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
KEYWORDS	3
1 Introduction	4
2 Conceptual foundation	4
2.1 Summary of scope and purpose	4
2.2 Tool impact, user demands, functionality	5
2.3 Target audience	11
3 Technical foundation	12
CONCLUSION	13
BIBLIOGRAPHY	13

**CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE**

Figures

Figure 1. Conceptual foundation of the proposed SIAC tool, with UF-NBS assessment being approached from two angles (red boxes) to achieve desired tool impacts (blue boxes). First, from an UF-NBS knowledge perspective, CLEARING HOUSE products, here particularly the trait-based UF-NBS typology, are put into operation. Second, the trait-based approach is applied to (potentially challenge-oriented) case-specific data..... 5

Figure 2. Non-exhaustive (tentative) list of tool functions (left), and the intended impacts of SIAC (middle) with respect to elicited user demands (rights). 7

Figure 3. Tree density (trees per hectare) at plot-level, as determined by SIAC. 9

Figure 4. Indicators for structural connectivity of tree-based entities. LNK denotes the number of links, i.e., connections between UF-NBS (left). CPL is the characteristic path length, i.e., the averaged distance to connected tree-based entities (right). Both parameters are derived from a nearest-neighbour-based network, where a connection is considered if no obstruction by buildings is found. In these examples, a better structural connectivity would be indicated by a higher number of links, and simultaneously, by a lower CPL..... 9

Figure 5. Estimation of UF-NBS benefits, here exemplified based on the indicators average carbon storage and average carbon sequestration. As shown, in addition to spatial data being generated or augmented by SIAC, short textual summaries are also provided to the user for convenience..... 11

Figure 6. Mockup of the SIAC tool user interface. The tabbed interface provides access to functions of the tool for managing input data, setting tool parameters, and for providing feedback to the user. . 12

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*CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE*

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the concept for the CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification (SIAC) tool. It outlines the intended scope and purpose of the tool, and intended tool impacts with respect to user demands. SIAC seeks to adopt a perspective of tree and tree-based entities to support rapid assessment of the state and potential benefits of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS). The SIAC tool is proposed as a plugin for the freely available, open-source desktop GIS QGIS, and is realized as a toolkits, i.e., a set of modules that encapsulate key functionalities.

KEYWORDS

Decision support tool; Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification tool; UF-NBS; trait-based analysis; tool development; CLEARING HOUSE

*CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE*

1 Introduction

This document outlines the intended Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification (SIAC) tool. It describes the objectives of tool development, and summarizes intended impacts with respect to user demands elicited previously in CLEARING HOUSE (M4.3). Below, first, the conceptual foundation of the tool is outlined. Second, technical aspects of the implementation are summarised.

2 Conceptual foundation

2.1 Summary of scope and purpose

SIAC is intended as a tool for the assessment of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS). To support this key objective, conceptually, SIAC approaches this assessment from two angles (Figure 1). First, from a UF-NBS knowledge perspective, SIAC is positioned to connect to and integrate other CLEARING HOUSE products. Here, a focus is particularly on the trait-based typology on UF-NBS developed earlier in the project (Scheuer et al., 2022). In order to make this CLEARING HOUSE product more accessible, a prototypical implementation of key aspects of this typology is a core development objective. Hence, SIAC is sought to adopt the suggested trait-based approach for the identification and classification of tree-based entities (cf. Box 1) and of UF-NBS, respectively. Subsequently, also the estimation of their potential impacts (benefits) is aligned to the trait-based approach. Second, with respect to the case study cities in CLEARING HOUSE, SIAC seeks to put this approach into operation on the basis of (potentially challenge-oriented) case-specific (geographic) data.

Box 1. Explanation of terms used.

Tree-based entity: Represents real-world objects that correspond to trees, or that are composed (that contain) one or more trees, including tree lines, groups of trees, but also larger features such as parks, gardens, or forests. In line with the typology developed by Scheuer et al. (2022), with the scope of this tool, tree-based entities are considered UF-NBS.

Trait-based approach: Here, a trait is understood as a discernible aggregate feature of UF-NBS, including spatial, morphological, contextual, structural, functional, or institutional characteristics. The trait-based modelling approach subsequently seeks to classify UF-NBS and estimate potential benefits as a function of such traits (Scheuer et al., 2022).

Canopy cover: Canopy cover refers to the area that is covered by the tree crowns of individual or grouped trees, delimited by the vertical projection of the (hypothetical) outermost perimeter of tree foliage to the underlying ground surface, with small openings and gaps being included (Jennings et al, 1999).

CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE

SIAC is primarily intended at assessing a status quo, i.e., current UF-NBS conditions. The intended spatial scales range from site level/micro-scale to city scale. However, by providing input data adapted to scenarios describing desired conditions, e.g., amended tree locations in anticipation of tree planting action, possible future conditions of UF-NBS may also be assessed within the envisaged scope of the tool.

Figure 1. Conceptual foundation of the proposed SIAC tool, with UF-NBS assessment being approached from two angles (red boxes) to achieve desired tool impacts (blue boxes). First, from an UF-NBS knowledge perspective, CLEARING HOUSE products, here particularly the trait-based UF-NBS typology, are put into operation. Second, the trait-based approach is applied to (potentially challenge-oriented) case-specific data.

2.2 Tool impact, user demands, functionality

CLEARING HOUSE previously elicited user demands for the development of UF-NBS decision-support tools (Wolff et al., 2021). Considering the aforementioned objectives and tool scope and purpose, SIAC is aligned to meet the following *user demands*:

- (i) Provide locally specific, operational indicators on UF-NBS;
- (ii) Raise awareness towards UF-NBS;
- (iii) Assess the relationship between urban grey buildings and green spaces;
- (iv) Model UF-NBS conditions; and thus,

***CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE***

- (v) Assess contributions (benefits) of specific UF-NBS to challenges/ecosystem services, e.g., heat mitigation, recreational benefits, etc.

Furthermore, with respect to these user demands, in line with development objectives and tool scope and purpose, SIAC is intended to have the following *key impacts*:

- (i) Provide a systematic, trait-based assessment and classification of UF-NBS entities on the basis of minimal (and possibly openly available) data;
- (ii) Facilitate cross-case comparison studies, due to the consistent classification of UF-NBS entities provided by the tool;
- (iii) Augment common land-use data with information derived from traits;
- (iv) Enable rapid (indicator-based) urban forest assessment, to summarize the state and potential benefits of UF-NBS
- (v) Identify potential areas of intervention for UF-NBS action, e.g., to improve connectivity of tree-based entities.

To realize these impacts, and hence, to meet identified user demands, SIAC implements various functions for the assessment of UF-NBS. Applying the proposed trait-based approach on case-specific data (cf. Table 1 for a non-exhaustive list of required data), conceptualized *functionalities* include:

- (i) Modelling of tree canopy;
- (ii) Assessment of spatial (topological) and morphological relationships between tree-based entities themselves and to urban (grey) features;
- (iii) Determines basic measures of (structural) connectivity;
- (iv) Conducts on-site assessment, specified e.g. on the basis of land-use categories, or based on tool-generated spatial analysis units.

Figure 2 summarizes the conceptualized tool functions, intended tool impacts, and the addressed user demands.

CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE

Figure 2. Non-exhaustive (tentative) list of tool functions (left), and the intended impacts of SIAC (middle) with respect to elicited user demands (rights).

CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE

Table 1. Non-exhaustive (tentative) list of input data required for the SIAC application.

Dataset	Format	Geometry Type	Remarks
Locations, species of trees (tree cadastral data)	Shapefile	Point	At a minimum, location of trees
Street network	Shapefile	Line	Street centerlines
Building footprints	Shapefile	Polygon	Building footprints/perimeters
Land-use	Shapefile	Polygon	Land-use attribute

SIAC puts a trait-based approach into operation for realizing intended tool impacts, e.g., for the classification of UF-NBS, or for the augmentation of land-use data with information derived from an assessment of traits. Moreover, to enable rapid UF-NBS assessment for summarizing UF-NBS conditions in a locally specific manner, SIAC determines selected indicators (cf. Table 2).

SIAC provides outputs either in the form of (i) generated geodata (shapefiles); (ii) augmented geodata, i.e., information written to a shapefile's attribute table; or (iii) summarily in the form of short text snippets. Such SIAC products are exemplified below. Figure 3 shows *tree density* (trees per hectare) at the level of plots, as an exemplary indicator-based geospatial SIAC product. Figure 4 exemplifies the *number of links* of tree-based entities as well as *characteristic path length* as two indicators of structural UF-NBS connectivity.

CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE

Figure 3. Tree density (trees per hectare) at plot-level, as determined by SIAC.

Figure 4. Indicators for structural connectivity of tree-based entities. LNK denotes the number of links, i.e., connections between UF-NBS (left). CPL is the characteristic path length, i.e., the averaged distance to connected tree-based entities (right). Both parameters are derived from a nearest-neighbour-based network, where a connection is considered if no obstruction by

CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE

buildings is found. In these examples, a better structural connectivity would be indicated by a higher number of links, and simultaneously, by a lower CPL.

Similar to the assessment of UF-NBS conditions as outlined above, also the potential benefits of UF-NBS are derived as a function of traits and/or indicators. This is exemplified in Figure 5. Here, potential benefits of UF-NBS are estimated based on the indicators *average carbon storage* and *average carbon sequestration*. Both indicators are in turn assessed as a function of total tree canopy cover (Nowak et al., 2013). The Figure exemplifies the text snippets provided by SIAC for the summarization of findings.

Table 2. Non-exhaustive (tentative) list of indicators implemented in the SIAC tool. Importantly, certain indicators are also used to express UF-NBS conditions. For example, the indicator total woody vegetation cover may also be considered a trait (a property) of spatial analysis units.

Indicator	Description	Unit
Tree count	Number of tree entities within assessed spatial analysis unit (e.g., per canopy, plot).	-
Tree density	Number of tree entities normalized per spatial analysis unit.	trees/ha
Total canopy-covered area	Total area covered by (closed) tree (woody vegetation) canopy, i.e., sum of canopy cover. This indicator may serve as a proxy for shaded area, but is not equivalent to the latter.	m ²
Canopy-covered area ratio	Share of an entity's area that is covered by canopy cover.	(%)
Total woody vegetation cover	The total area covered by woody vegetation. This indicator is considered to be equivalent to the indicator total canopy-covered area.	m ²
Number of links (LNK)	The number of connections (links) within a nearest neighbour-based network of tree canopy (Urban and Keitt, 2001; Pascual-Horta and Saura, 2006). A connection is considered between two given tree-based entities if it is not obstructed, i.e., intersected by a building.	-
Characteristic path length (CPL)	The averaged distance between connected tree-based entities (Urban and Keitt, 2001; Pascual-Horta and Saura, 2006; cf. also number of links).	m
Number of components	Threshold-dependent number of components (groups of interconnected tree canopies).	-
Average carbon storage	The average amount of carbon stored as a function of tree canopy cover (Nowak et al., 2013).	kg C/m ² of tree cover
Average carbon sequestration	The average amount of carbon sequestered annually as a function of tree canopy cover. (Nowak et al., 2013).	kg C/m ² of tree cover, per year

CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE

Figure 5. Estimation of UF-NBS benefits, here exemplified based on the indicators average carbon storage and average carbon sequestration. As shown, in addition to spatial data being generated or augmented by SIAC, short textual summaries are also provided to the user for convenience.

2.3 Target audience

In light of the intended implementation as a GIS plugin that requires certain technical skills, and with respect to the scope and purpose, SIAC is aimed particularly at *practitioners from urban planning, greenspace planning and management, and at research and academia.*

CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE

3 Technical foundation

SIAC is conceptualized as a plugin (Figure 6) for the open-source desktop GIS software QGIS (version 3.26.0 or newer). On the one hand, this is in contrast to the originally proposed tool, that was foreseen as an online application. However, the envisaged scope and purpose of SIAC require leveraging GIS functionality that is not necessarily feasible to be implemented as an online tool. On the other hand, integration into QGIS as an established software builds on a readily and freely available tool with powerful functions for data analysis and visualization, and in so doing, also provides opportunities for facilitating tool dissemination, e.g., via the available plugin repositories, and for increasing tool adoption.

Figure 6. Mockup of the SIAC tool user interface. The tabbed interface provides access to functions of the tool for managing input data, setting tool parameters, and for providing feedback to the user.

SIAC is conceptualized as a toolkit, i.e., a set of modules. Each module encapsulates certain functionalities. Tentatively, these modules include: (i) *Tree Configuration Assessment and Classification (TCAC)*, i.e., the assessment of spatial-morphological planting patterns, modelling of tree canopy, and a classification of trees as solitary, grouped, etc.; (ii) *Topology Modeller (TOPOMOD)*, i.e., the assessment of spatial (topological) relationships between tree-based entities themselves (i.e., an assessment of structural connectivity), and to urban (grey) features such as streets and buildings; (iii) *Site Assessment (SITA)*, i.e., the assessment of specific spatial entities, e.g., regarding their composition (morphology); and *Computation of Indicators (COIN)*, a module dedicated to the calculation of selected indicators. Further modules, e.g., *DATA PROCESSOR*, realize functions to generate input data for the various tool modules. The modular concept is chosen to facilitate tool maintenance, and possible future integration of additional functions. It also allows integrating third-party tools to support UF-NBS

*CLEARING HOUSE Spatial Impact Assessment and Classification Tool.
Concept Note on the development of decision-support tools in CLEARING HOUSE*

modelling and assessment, e.g., urban morphometrics for modelling and quantitatively assessing urban form (Fleischmann, 2019).

CONCLUSION

This document informs on the conceptual foundation of the SIAC tool, including the proposed scope and purpose. Intended tool impacts, addressed user demands, and key functionality to realize these impacts are summarily presented. Importantly, the information shown is non-exhaustive and tentative, particularly with regard to data requirements, and the considered traits and indicators.

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